

CardioGuide: An Electrical and Imaging Cardiac Graphical User Interface for experimental electrophysiology studies

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Abstract—Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most frequent sustained cardiac arrhythmia, affecting up to 2% of the world population. For its treatment, commercial systems, based on electrical mapping, are prone to errors and catheters have a limited number of electrodes (i.e low spatial resolution). In recent decades, important advances were made in the understanding of AF and development of therapeutic strategies, obtained through the optical mapping, considered the gold standard in mapping cardiac electrical activity. Recently, we developed an experimental setup, combining electrical and panoramic optical mapping to customize AF maps, through an animal model with isolated rabbit heart. Although many efforts have been made by the HEartLab into the experimental setup development, the experiment is of high complexity, where several variables and circumstances (Surgery, Setup Variables, 3D Heart reconstruction, Acquisition of cardiac signals and 3D Mapping) could affect the outcomes, consequently, AF characterization. To overcome the current obstacles, and aiming standardization of the procedures and protocols, this study presents the CardioGuide, an Electrical and Imaging Cardiac Graphical User Interface made to assist in experiments, allowing it to be fully logged and ensure quality control of the experiment for the researchers. This platform has two modules, that are developed in LabVIEW and Python 3, and it's structured in a tab-view mode. CardioGuide has been validated off-line, with retrospective experiments with the AF model, as such, the system provides all of the information registered through reports, that are accessible through PDF format. CardioGuide development is important to maintain the quality control of the experiments, ensuring that protocols during experimental procedures are followed and all of the details are being properly logged.

Keywords — atrial fibrillation, panoramic optical mapping, animal experiment, software development, graphic user interface.

I. INTRODUCTION

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most frequent sustained cardiac arrhythmia, affecting up to 2% of the world population [1]. This arrhythmia is characterized by the collapse of organized atria cardiac electrical activity [1], with

consequent deterioration of the mechanical function, increasing significantly the chances of occurrence of thromboembolic phenomena [2].

The mechanisms responsible for AF trigger and maintenance could differ from patient to patient, and multiples can coexist simultaneously [3]. For its treatment, commercial systems, based on electrical mapping, are affected by factors such as far field, limited number of electrodes and several others [4], hampering true electrophysiology behavior of this arrhythmia, and limiting success rates of treatments.

In recent decades, experimental and simulation studies have allowed researchers to improve current understanding of this complex arrhythmia, which were later translated to clinic. Studies where optical mapping have been conducted, throughout animal and human experiments, considered the gold standard in mapping cardiac electrical, allowed to observe the AF mechanisms and their spatiotemporal characteristics [4-9].

Current limitations of the commercial electroanatomic systems can be surpassed through the benefit of the optical mapping, where both optical and electrical mapping could be used simultaneously, and the respective recordings undergoing AF and biomarkers compared, for latter customization of the electrical mapping. Our research group has been working on it, and have developed a setup combining electrical and panoramic optical mapping to study AF in an animal model with isolated rabbit heart under AF [10]. In this study we present a recently developed platform called CardioGuide, where equipment's are integrated and can be managed by a Graphical User Interface (GUI). With CardioGuide, all steps needed to be performed during the animal model experiment, since the arrival of the animal in the laboratory facilities, followed by the solutions preparation, anesthesia, euthanasia, surgery, AF induction, signals acquisitions and other protocols are registered in the GUI, allowing the standardization of the experimental procedures and ensuring quality control of the data generated, with the ability to track parameters and variables used in any experiment, such as temperatures, animal and heart data, the solutions and dyes used, among others.

Fig 1. Diagram of the systems and subsystems of the GUI

II. METHODS

Figure 1 presents a schematic representation of the CardioGuide system. The systematic process starts with the registration of procedures, verification of the systems and the 3D mapping generation, the objective is to create a repeatable and intuitive sequence for quality control of the experiment, report acquisition, 3D mapping, and electromechanical control. Summarizing, all the information obtained from the components of the process (Chemical solutions, Euthanasia, Langendorff setup, Noninvasive electrical mapping, AF induction, Panoramic optical mapping and Epicardium electrical mapping) are registered by the platform.

In Figure 2 is presented the GUI's main tabs, developed in Python 3 using the framework PyQt5, which are: Welcome, Preparation, Verification, Experimental Procedure, 3D Visualization, and Final Checklist.

Fig 2. Front page of the developed GUI developed in Python with its respective tabs

A) *Welcome*: Informs the user what is the objective of the program, making the initial log of the people present during the experiment, and other data such as date, time, room temperature and functions of each member participating the experiment.

B) *Preparations*: Helps the user with the steps needed to be made before the experiment proper is started. Such as solutions, and the heart extraction. Subdivided in:

- **Anesthetic Solution**: This tab contains the Animal Data necessary to properly conduct the experiment, and the steps to the General Anesthetic Preparation. The recommended dosage given to the animal, is based on formulas that takes in the weight of the animal as a variable, however, parameters can be changed, and the dosage administered can be changed.
- **Harvesting and Perfusion Solutions**: Tyrode Solution – solution that is isotonic with the interstitial fluid, used to provide nutrition to the heart; and Cardioplegia Solution – stops the heart from beating, conserving its electrical activity.
- **Optical Mapping Solutions**: Dye Solution – with the electrical activity of the heart and the stimulation from the LEDs the dye fluoresces in the infrared, which is captured by the cameras; and Uncoupler Solution – inhibits the contraction of the heart, and as with the other solutions, parameters and even solutes can be changed.
- **Other Solutions**: Tank Solution – used to maintain the heart temperature, recirculates in the tank with an external circulation water bath; and Acetylcholine Solution – with the correct stimulation induces atrial fibrillation.
- **Extraction Data**: Contain data of the heart extraction procedure, such as time; the animal vitals during the experiment – Flow Rate, Heart Frequency and Arterial Pressure; and the heart data – Weight, Height and Width;

additional observations can also be made about the procedure.

C) Verification: This tab has the function of guiding the user to verify if all the systems used during the experiment are in perfect working order. Divided in:

- **Langendorff System:** Steps are taken to ensure that there are no leaks in the system, and all the adjacent apparatus are working properly, such as the pumps and the water baths.
- **Optical Mapping:** All the subsystems that are part of the Optical Mapping System needs to be working, including LEDs, Gig-E Cameras and the step motor. All Gig-E cameras must be placed 120° from one another and be equidistant from the center of the tank. How to properly initiate and configure the panoramic mapping software, after careful consideration the software StreamPix [11] was concluded to be the best for our use case, the images will be recorded in RAW data with a resolution of 1604 by 1100 pixels and at more than 600 frames per second.
- **Electrical Mapping:** Similarly, to the Optical Mapping, divided by the subsystems – EcoFlexMEA, Tank Electrodes, and the Open Ephys hardware and software. The EcoFlexMEA is responsible to capture the invasive electrical data, directly from the epicardium, the tank electrodes capture the electrical data away from the heart simulating electrodes placed on the animal's torso. The Open Ephys is an open-source platform used to capture, display and process electrical data from multiple (up to 256) sources.
- **Screen Capture:** Instructs the user as to how to properly setup the OBS Studio [12]. This software is used to capture the computer screen during the experiment, as its important in case it is needed to double check the parameters during the experimentation.

D) Experimental Procedure: Guides the user as to how to properly conduct the experiment, starting from the Langendorff system on how to place the heart inside the tank, to when and how to use each solution, and what to do if the heart stops beating. The Optical Mapping and Electrical Mapping almost always will be performed at the same time so it is important that the steps on how to capture both synchronized be clear and well thought out. In this tab of the platform, it will also instruct the user on how and where to properly save the optical and electrical files. The main purpose of the experiment is to study the atrial fibrillation, so this area will also guide the user on how to properly set up the biostimulator and what are the best parameters to use and when.

E) 3D Visualization: Once the 3D of the heart is obtained, as described below (please see subsection *E.1*), it is uploaded to the Python module of CardioGuide, where using the Mayavi library and its function called *triangular_mesh*, we are able to plot and visualize the 3D images, with the ability to add different shapes and forms into the plot. With this configuration, we can determine the points of interest and then save it in an image format for further analysis.

E.1 3D Surface: This module has been developed in LabVIEW (Figure 3), and allows to rotate and capture images of the heart, to later be turned into a 3D Model of the heart where the panoramic data gathered during the experiment can be projected into. This software is used to capture the images of the heart as it rotates in

an axis connected to a step motor, it was also developed in LabVIEW 2021 SP1. It functions sending a string to an Arduino Uno connected to the computer via USB, containing the angle to rotate the motor by. The program has 3 modes of operation: Number of Images, Move Number Steps, Move For (Degrees). The program runs a while loop until the number of iterations remaining to be made is equals to zero. It communicates with the Arduino with the *Serial Palette* functions; it opens the Serial Port with the *VISA Configure Serial Port* function and writes to the Serial Port with the *Visa Write* function. The information written in each loop contains the angle of rotation expected in that iteration and have the format *'1/n#Angle'* where *#Angle* is a float. The Arduino reads this string and rotates the motor by the amount specified. After each rotation, in the LabVIEW program, an image is takes of the heart after a delay – that can also be determined by the user -, so that the heart can stop moving due to the acceleration and deceleration of the motor. The angle is computed different for each mode of operation, to the Number of Images mode it is calculated as 360 divided by the number of images desired by the user; to the Move Number Steps its always 1.8°, and the user chooses how many 1.8° steps the motor will make; to the Move For (Degrees) the user directly chooses the angle of each rotation and the best approximation, based on the microstep of the step motor, is used. In the Number of Images and in the Move For (Degrees) modes a full rotation is always made. To take the images the *IMAQdx Palette* [13] was used. The *IMAQdx Open Camera* function was used to open the camera and to set the exposure, that can also be controlled by the user. Each image is capture using the *IMAQdx snap* function, each image captured is also displayed live to the user. After each image is captures the *saveNumberedImage* Sub VI, based on the RHYTHM [14] software, saves each image as *'Image#Number.tiff'* where *#Number* is the number in sequence when the image was taken; also saves an accompanying text file for each image with the angle of the heart it was taken.

Fig 3. Front page of the 3D Surface software in use during an experiment

F) Final Checklist: Steps to be taken after the experiment is done, to ensure the proper disposal of chemical and biological residue; ensure that the data gathered during the experiment is properly backed up and that all chemicals and materials used are properly stored.

G) Report: Using the FPDF library, we are able to generate PDF reports from the ground-up. We take all of the elements that are placed in the GUI (such as spaces for user input, combo boxes and date/time fields) and place them inside an A4 virtual paper, with configurations to be printed as soon we need it. All the PDFs generated with the FPDF library, cover all the elements that needs the users-input, but the tables that are met in the Preparations tab and sub-tabs, to be saved for

later analysis, we used the *QPrinter* function inside PyQt5, to pick the data inside the tables and transfer then to a PDF file.

H) Save State/Load State: Besides the method to generate reports and save them in PDF files, explained above, CardioGuide also has an option present in the *Welcome* tab, to save the state of all the variables inserted by the user to a config file, through the *pyqtconfig* library that transforms this file containing all the variables, into a JSON file that can be easily accessed. When its needed, CardioGuide can also load the JSON file, restoring the state of the GUI with the previous inserted variables.

III. RESULTS

Validation of CardioGuide was performed using data of a pilot experiment to guarantee the quality of data generated and its replicability [10]. In Fig. 4 is shown an example using the validation data, as to how the information is displayed to the researcher in the PDF report. In total there are 7 PDFs that are generated, dividing all of the information into sections, making it easier for the researcher to track a specific information that may have occurred during the experiment for later analysis.

Fig. 4: Example of how the reports display the information retrieved from CardioGuide – Section 3 – System Verification.

To illustrate some of the variables generated throughout the experimental setup and platform, Fig 5A presents the 3D surface obtained of a rabbit heart, after segmentation of the correspondent volume, obtained with 50 different field of view images (.tiff) of the heart, one for every 7.2° per rotation step, completing 360°. Figs. 5B shows an 2D optical fluorescence map, color-coded according to normalized fluorescence potential, and Figure 5C shows a 3D heart potential map, obtained by the panoramic optical mapping, after heart segmentation and preprocessing optical signals.

Fig. 5: The 3D obtained of the epicardia surface (A); Voltage maps generated by camera (B); Voltage map projected on the 3D surface (C).

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study is presented the CardioGuide – an Electrical and Imaging Cardiac Graphical User Interface, an auxiliary platform tool to help standardizing the control variables and protocols of experiment. For future releases, CardioGuide will be made available online, as its being developed in an open-source language, to help and guide other researchers that might be experiencing the same problems regarding experimental quality and data control.

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